

A STUDY ON LEARNING STYLES OF COASTAL AREA STUDENTS STUDYING IN HIGH SCHOOL LEVEL

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Introduction:

"Learning is the true imperishable riches; all other things are not riches. A man without education is like a marble in a quarry which does not show its inherent beauty till the skill of a polisher fetches out all its beauty" (Naik, 1968). Man becomes 'man' through education. Man is an animal, both from his passions and his reason. Education fashions and models him for society. There are generally two aspects of human life. One is biological and the other is social or cultural or spiritual. Human life can never be reduced to its biological existence. His life can only be glorified through education, and it is only the cultural or social aspect of human life which signifies his supreme position and thus constitutes the noblest work of god. According to Nunn (1975) "Education is the complete development of the individuality of the child so that he can make an original contribution to human life according to the best of his capacity."

Learning Styles:

Learning styles are, in its simplest form, approaches or ways of learning. It involves learning methods that are presumed to allow that individual to learn best. It is commonly believed that most people favour some particular methods of interacting with, taking in, and processing stimuli or information. The idea of 'individualized learning styles' originated in the 1970s. It has gained popularity in recent years, based on this concept. It has been proposed that teachers should assess the learning styles of their students and adapt their classroom methods to best fit each student's learning style. Learning styles is an overarching term covering a spectrum of modalities, preferences and strategies by which individual absorb, process and respond to situations and input resulting in learning.

Learning style is defined as "the complex manner in which and conditions under which learners most efficiently and most effectively perceive process, store and recall what they are attempting to learn"- James and Gardener

Significance of the Study:

One of the most basic aspects of learning styles is that it concentrates on the way in which we initially receive information from our sense organs. It is also called as receptive learning style. Here the VAK (Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic) learning styles play a vital role. Each and every student has VAK learning styles. A style that involves visualizing information in mind's eye, favouring reading and watching over touching and hearing is called visual learning style. A style that favours listening as the best approach to learning is Auditory learning style. A style that involves learning by touching manipulating objects and doing things is Kinesthetic learning style. Though we have variety of styles, the investigator selects only the VAK learning styles for his study because the investigator like to find out the impact of VAK learning styles of the students. He would like to search for the VAK learning styles of Coastal Area Students Studying in High School Level. He also likes to know the relationship among the Visual, Auditory and Kinesthetic learners. Thus, this area of study is chosen for study.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of Coastal Area Students Studying in High School Level
- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of high school level
- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to gender.
- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to age.
- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to locality of school.
- ✓ To find the level of VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to medium of instruction.

Hypothesis:

Hypothesis and null hypothesis and for my present study, I have framed null hypothesis.

Method of Study:

The normative Survey method has been followed to find out level of VAK learning styles of high school level students in coastal area. This tool has been administered to a random sample of 350 high school level students in coastal area for various districts in tamilnadu. The data collected from the sample has been subjected to Descriptive and Differential analysis

Analysis of Data and Interpretation:

Gender and Learning Styles: It is inferred from the below table-1 that the calculated 't' value of VAK (2.56, 2.11 and 4.06) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is

rejected. So there is significant difference in the VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to gender. Based on the calculated mean score, it is found that the Female students (M=9.70) are better than male students (M=8.79) in Visual learning styles. Female students (M=11.08) are better than male students (M=10.35) in Auditory learning styles. Female students (M=10.87) are better than male students (M=9.22) in Kinesthetic learning styles.

Age and Learning Styles:

It is inferred from the above table -2 that, the calculated ‘t’ value of VAK (1.05, 0.90 and 1.66) is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference in the VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to age.

Locality of School and Learning Styles:

It is inferred from the above table-3 that, the calculated ‘t’ value of Visual (2.83) and Kinesthetic (2.97) learners are greater than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. So there is significant difference in the Visual and Kinesthetic learning styles of high school level students with regard to locality of school. Based on the calculated mean score, it is found that the Rural school (M=9.78) students are better than Urban school (M=8.77) students in Visual learning style. Rural school (M=10.81) students are better than Urban school (M=10.62) students in Auditory learning style.

The calculated ‘t’ value of Auditory (0.56) learners is less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference in the Auditory learning style of high school level students with regard to locality of school.

Medium of Instruction and Learning Styles:

It is inferred from the above table-4 that the calculated ‘t’ value of Visual learners (2.98) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. So there is significant difference in the Visual learning style of high school level students with regard to medium of instruction. English medium students (10.07) are better than Tamil medium students (8.90) in Visual learning style.

The calculated ‘t’ values of Auditory (1.36) and Kinesthetic (1.51) learners are less than the table value (1.96) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. So there is no significant difference in the Auditory and Kinesthetic learning styles of high school level students with regard to medium of instruction

Table 1: Level of VAK Learning Styles of Coastal Area Students Studying In High School Level

Learning Styles	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Visual	79	22.57	82	23.43	189	54.00
Auditory	55	15.71	184	52.57	111	31.71
Kinesthetic	93	26.57	164	46.86	93	26.57

It is inferred from the above table (1) that the Coastal Area Students Studying in High School Level have 22.57% of low, 23.43% of moderate and 54.00% high level of Visual learning style, 15.71% of low, 52.57% of moderate and 31.71% high level of Auditory learning style and 26.57% of low, 46.86% of moderate and 26.57% high level of Kinesthetic learning style.

Table 2: Difference in VAK Learning Styles of High School Level Students with Regard to Gender

Learning Style	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ Value	Table Value	Remark
Visual	Male	178	8.79	3.57	2.56	1.96	S
	Female	172	9.70	3.11			
Auditory	Male	178	10.35	3.49	2.11	1.96	S
	Female	172	11.08	2.99			
Kinesthetic	Male	178	10.87	4.23	4.06	1.96	S
	Female	172	9.22	3.33			

Table 3: Difference in VAK Learning Styles of High School Level Students with Regard to Age

Learning Styles	Age	N	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ Value	Table Value	Remark
Visual	16 and Below	251	9.36	3.26	1.05	1.96	NS
	17 and Above	99	8.92	3.67			
Auditory	16 and Below	251	10.81	3.24	0.90	1.96	NS
	17 and Above	99	10.45	3.35			
Kinesthetic	16 and Below	251	9.83	3.78	1.66	1.96	NS
	17 and Above	99	10.63	4.15			

Table 4: Difference in VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to locality of school

Learning Style	Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ Value	Table Value	Remark
Visual	Rural	162	9.78	3.45	2.83	1.96	S

	Urban	188	8.77	3.25			
Auditory	Rural	162	10.81	3.24	0.56	1.96	NS
	Urban	188	10.62	3.31			
Kinesthetic	Rural	162	9.40	3.59	2.97	1.96	S
	Urban	188	10.62	4.07			

Table 5: Difference in VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to Medium of Instruction

Learning Style	Medium	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark
Visual	Tamil	249	8.90	3.35	2.98	1.96	S
	English	101	10.07	3.32			
Auditory	Tamil	249	10.86	3.34	1.36	1.96	NS
	English	101	10.35	3.09			
Kinesthetic	Tamil	249	10.24	4.01	1.51	1.96	NS
	English	101	9.58	3.59			

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is significant difference in the VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the VAK learning styles of high school level students with regard to age.
- ✓ There is significant difference in the Visual and Kinesthetic learning styles of high school level students with regard to locality of school. There is no significant difference in the Auditory learning style of high school level students with regard to locality of school.
- ✓ There is significant difference in the Visual learning style of high school level students with regard to medium of instruction. There is no significant difference in the Auditory and Kinesthetic learning styles of high school level students with regard to medium of instruction.

Recommendations:

- ✓ On the basis of the results obtained from the analysis, the following recommendations are given:
- ✓ Proper motivation should be given to the students to develop better learning style.
- ✓ Teachers should encourage the students to develop their preferred learning styles.
- ✓ Teachers should give sensory learning style practice to the students to improve their VAK learning styles.
- ✓ Teacher and parents should find the interest in the minds of students about their learning styles and help them to sharpening their preferred learning style.
- ✓ Teachers understand the family background of the students and teach them accordingly.
- ✓ Parents must create good learning environment in the family.
- ✓ Parents should find out and encourage the children's preferred learning styles.

Conclusion:

Even though there are some limitations in the present study, it is evident that the presence of learning styles among students. The teachers should understand the learning styles of the students and teach them accordingly. The parents also take care on students and understand their learning style and motivate them accordingly. It also means that the teachers should aware on the learning styles, i.e., they should be men who know what is the way of students to understand the subject matters. Then only they are able to bring in all these experiences into the classroom to make the teaching style more relevant and meaningful. The recommendations given by the investigator may be very helpful in creating more awareness regarding the learning styles of the students.

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